

THERMAL SHOCK OF SYMMETRIC CROSS-PLY LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

The dynamic behavior of symmetric cross-ply laminated plates having two parallel simply supported edges and subjected to sudden surface heating is investigated. The solution obtained consists of an exact representation of the quasi-static deflection plus a Galerkin approximation for the associated dynamic deflection. Effects of laminate stacking sequence and support conditions upon the response are illustrated through numerical examples.

INTRODUCTION

The dynamic response of thin-walled structures to rapidly applied heating represents a major problem in various mechanical and aerospace applications. Thermally induced vibration of an isotropic plate has been studied by Boley and Barber¹ and a number of other researchers²⁻⁷. Less attention has been given to the dynamic thermoelastic response of anisotropic and nonhomogeneous structures. Exceptions include the work of Kao and Pao⁸ who considered symmetric cross-ply plates having all edges simply supported, and a study by the author⁹ dealing with thermal shock of orthotropic plates possessing two simply supported edges. The latter investigation is extended in this paper to the case of symmetric cross-ply laminates.

GOVERNING EQUATIONS

According to classical laminated plate theory, the transverse motion of a thin, symmetric¹⁰ cross-ply plate subject to a temperature rise $T(z,t)$ is governed by the equation

$$D_{11} \frac{\partial^4 w}{\partial x^4} + 2(D_{12} + 2D_{66}) \frac{\partial^4 w}{\partial x^2 \partial y^2} + D_{22} \frac{\partial^4 w}{\partial y^4} + \rho h \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial t^2} = - \frac{\partial^2 M_x^T}{\partial x^2} - \frac{\partial^2 M_y^T}{\partial y^2} \quad (1)$$

in which $w(x,y,t)$ is the deflection of the plate middle surface, ρ denotes the mass density, h is the plate thickness and D_{ij} are the laminate bending stiffnesses. Also appearing in Eq. (1) are the thermal moments defined by

$$(M_x^T, M_y^T) = \sum_{k=1}^N [(\gamma_1)_k, (\gamma_2)_k] \int_{z_{(k-1)}}^{z_k} T z dz \quad (2)$$

where

$$(\gamma_i)_k = (\bar{Q}_{i1} \alpha_x + \bar{Q}_{i2} \alpha_y)_k \quad (3)$$

The transformed reduced stiffness coefficients $(\bar{Q}_{ij})_k$ and the thermal expansion coefficients $(\alpha_x, \alpha_y)_k$ characterize the effective orthotropic properties of the k^{th} layer ($z_{k-1} < z < z_k$, $k=1,2,\dots,N$) in the direction of the plate coordinates (x,y) .

We consider a thermal excitation consisting of a suddenly applied heat flux q_0 over the surface $z=h/2$, while the surface $z=-h/2$ is insulated. The temperature rise in this case is

$$T = \frac{hq_0}{k} \left[\frac{\beta t}{\pi^2} + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{z}{h} + \frac{1}{2} \right)^2 - \frac{1}{6} - \frac{2}{\pi^2} \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^j}{j^2} e^{-j^2 \beta t} \cos j\pi \left(\frac{z}{h} + \frac{1}{2} \right) \right] \quad (4)$$

Here $\beta = \pi^2 \kappa / h^2$, $\kappa = k / \rho c$, with k and ρc denoting the coefficient of thermal conductivity in the z -direction and the heat capacity of the layer material, respectively. For the temperature variation (4) the thermal moments (2) can be expressed as

$$(M_x^T, M_y^T) = \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} (E_m(t), F_m(t)) \sin \alpha_m x \quad (5)$$

where $\alpha_m = m\pi/a$ and

$$(E_m(t), F_m(t)) = \begin{cases} \frac{4}{m\pi} (f_1(t), f_2(t)) & m = \text{odd} \\ 0 & m = \text{even} \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

in which

$$f_j(t) = \frac{q_0}{2k} \left\{ \sum_{k=1}^N \frac{(\gamma_j)_k}{3} (z_k^3 - z_{k-1}^3) - \frac{4h^3}{\pi^4} \sum_{k=1}^N (\gamma_j)_k \cdot \sum_{j=1,3,\dots}^{\infty} \frac{e^{-j^2 \beta t}}{j^4} \sin \frac{j\pi}{2} \left[\sin \frac{j\pi z_k}{h} - \frac{j\pi z_k}{h} \cos \frac{j\pi z_k}{h} - \sin \frac{j\pi z_{k-1}}{h} + \frac{j\pi z_{k-1}}{h} \cos \frac{j\pi z_{k-1}}{h} \right] \right\} \quad (j=1,2) \quad (7)$$

SOLUTION

The middle-surface deflection w may be regarded as the sum of two terms, namely

$$w = w_1(x, y, t) + w_2(x, y, t) \quad (8)$$

where w_1 represents the quasi-static deflection satisfying the differential equation (1) when the inertia term ($\rho h \partial^2 w / \partial t^2$) is set equal to zero, together with the prescribed boundary conditions. The dynamic deflection w_2 must then satisfy (1) with the thermal loading terms ($\partial^2 M_x^T / \partial x^2$ and $\partial^2 M_y^T / \partial y^2$) ignored, along with homogeneous boundary conditions. Assuming that the plate is initially at rest, w_2 must also satisfy the conditions $w_2(x, y, 0) = -w_1(x, y, 0)$ and $\dot{w}_2(x, y, 0) = -\dot{w}_1(x, y, 0)$.

For the case of a plate with edges $x=0, a$ simply supported, the quasistatic deflection w_1 can be expressed as

$$w_1 = \sum_{m=1,3,\dots} Y_m^{(1)}(y, t) \sin \alpha_m x \quad (9)$$

Following the approach given in an earlier investigation⁹, it can be shown that the form of the general solution for $Y_m^{(1)}$ depends upon the values of the roots ζ of the characteristic equation

$$D_{11} - 2(D_{12} + 2D_{66})\zeta^2 + D_{22}\zeta^4 = 0 \quad (10)$$

For most fiber-reinforced laminates the roots of (10) are complex, i.e., $\zeta = \pm s \pm ri$ ($s, r > 0$), in which case

$$Y_m^{(1)} = K_m(t) + [A_m(t) \cos \alpha_m r y + B_m(t) \sin \alpha_m r y] \cosh \alpha_m s y + [C_m(t) \cos \alpha_m r y + D_m(t) \sin \alpha_m r y] \sinh \alpha_m s y \quad (11)$$

where $K_m(t) = E_m(t)/\alpha_m^2 D_{11}$, and $A_m(t)$, $B_m(t)$, $C_m(t)$ and $D_m(t)$ are determined through application of prescribed edge conditions on $y = \pm b/2$. Solutions corresponding to real, equal or unequal roots of (10) can be determined following the procedure presented in Ref. 9.

An approximate solution for the dynamic deflection can be found by assuming w_2 to be of the form

$$w_2 = \sum_m \sum_n Y_n^{(2)}(y) \sin \alpha_m x B_{mn}(t) \quad (12)$$

in which $Y_n^{(2)}(y)$ are taken as the appropriate eigenfunctions defining the normal modes of vibration of a uniform beam. Following the Galerkin approach, expression (12) for w_2 is substituted into the governing differential equation [Eq. (1) with the right-hand side replaced by zero], and the residual is required to be orthogonal to each eigenfunction $Y_n^{(2)}(y)$. Use of the orthogonality properties of the eigenfunctions then leads to a system of ordinary differential equations in time, having the form

$$\ddot{B}_{mn}(t) + G_{mn} \dot{B}_{mn}(t) + \sum_{q \neq n} H_{mqn} B_{mq}(t) = R_{mn}(t) \quad (m, n, q = 1, 3, \dots) \quad (13)$$

where

$$G_{mn} = [D_{11} \alpha_m^4 I_{nn} - 2(D_{12} + 2D_{66}) \alpha_m^2 J_{qn} + D_{22} K_{nn}] / \rho h I_{nn}$$

$$H_{mqn} = [-2(D_{12} + 2D_{66}) \alpha_m^2 J_{qn}] / \rho h I_{nn}, \quad R_{mn}(t) = -L_{mn} / I_{nn} \quad (14)$$

and

$$I_{nn} = \int_{-b/2}^{b/2} [Y_n^{(2)}]^2 dy, \quad J_{qn} = \int_{-b/2}^{b/2} \frac{d^2 Y_q^{(2)}}{dy^2} Y_n^{(2)} dy$$

$$K_{nn} = \int_{-b/2}^{b/2} \frac{d^4 Y_n^{(2)}}{dy^4} Y_n^{(2)} dy, \quad L_{mn}(t) = \int_{-b/2}^{b/2} \ddot{Y}_m^{(1)} Y_n^{(2)} dy \quad (15)$$

In addition to satisfying (13), the functions $B_{mn}(t)$ must satisfy the initial conditions

$$B_{mn}(0) = 0, \quad \dot{B}_{mn}(0) = -M_{mn} / I_{nn} \quad (16)$$

in which

$$M_{mn} = \int_{-b/2}^{b/2} \dot{Y}_m^{(1)} Y_n^{(2)} dy \quad (17)$$

Solutions to (13) and (16) have been obtained using the Runge-Kutta-Gill¹² method of numerical integration. All results presented in the following section were calculated by taking an upper limit of 5 for m and n in (9) and (12). Furthermore, in order to avoid numerical difficulties associated with an infinite value of $R_{mn}(t)$ at time $t=0$, the lower limit for the numerical integration was taken as $t = 1.0 \times 10^{-5}$ s rather than zero. A time step of 1.0×10^{-5} s was employed. These values were shown previously to yield acceptable results for the displacements in isotropic and orthotropic homogeneous plates.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The preceding formulation has been applied to three-layer symmetric cross-ply plates, having dimensions 0.025 in x 10 in x 10 in, and constructed of AS/3501 graphite/epoxy. Thermoelastic properties for a layer of this material are¹³

$$\begin{aligned}
 E_{11} &= 20.0 \times 10^6 \text{ psi} & E_{22} &= 1.30 \times 10^6 \text{ psi} & G_{12} &= 1.03 \times 10^6 \text{ psi} \\
 \nu_{12} &= 0.30 & \alpha_{11} &= -0.167 \times 10^{-6} \text{ } ^\circ\text{F}^{-1} & \alpha_{22} &= 15.6 \times 10^{-6} \text{ } ^\circ\text{F}^{-1} \\
 \rho &= 1.50 \times 10^{-4} \text{ lb s}^2/\text{in}^4 & k_z &= 9.63 \times 10^{-6} \text{ Btu/in s}^\circ\text{F} & \kappa &= 6.98 \times 10^{-4} \text{ in}^2/\text{s}
 \end{aligned}$$

Plots of surface temperatures versus time resulting from an assumed heat input of $q_0 = 0.10 \text{ Btu/in}^2 \text{ s}$ are shown in Fig. 1. Since the properties of this material may be considered temperature-independent only over a relatively small temperature range, attention is restricted here to the response within the time period $0 < t < 0.10 \text{ s}$, during which the temperature rise is less than 100°F .

Fig. 1 Temperature variation at (a) $x = -h/2$, (b) $x = h/2$.

As a first example, consider the case of a $0^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ$ laminate having all edges simply supported. The calculated deflected shape of the plate middle surface at the instant $t = 0.10 \text{ s}$ is plotted in Fig. 2. Note that the maximum displacement occurs at approximately $(5, \pm 2.5) \text{ in}$. Fig. 3 shows the time variations of the quasistatic deflection w_1 and the total deflection w at both the midpoint and the point of maximum deflection.

Fig. 2 Deflected shape of a $0^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ$ simply supported plate.

Fig. 3 Histories of w_1 and w at (a) $x = 5 \text{ in}$, $y = 0$ and (b) $x = 5 \text{ in}$, $y = \pm 2.5 \text{ in}$ of a $0^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ$ simply supported plate.

Next consider the case in which the plate edges $y=\pm b/2$ are clamped. The transverse deflections of the middle surface at $t=0.1s$ for $0^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ$ and $90^\circ/0^\circ/90^\circ$ laminates (plotted to the same vertical scale) are shown in Figs. 4 and 5. The maximum deflection is seen to occur at the center of the $0^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ$ plate, and at approximately (1.5,0)in. and (8.5,0)in for the $90^\circ/0^\circ/90^\circ$ plate. Histories of w_1 and w for the two laminates are presented in Figs. 6 and 7. The deflections are considerably larger for the latter configuration.

Fig. 4 Deflected shape of a $0^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ$ plate, clamped at $y = \pm 5$ in.

Fig. 5 Deflected shape of a $90^\circ/0^\circ/90^\circ$ plate, clamped at $y = \pm 5$ in.

For the particular laminates and thermal excitation considered here, the maximum total dynamic deflections are not significantly greater than the corresponding quasistatic deflections. The relatively less important role that inertia plays in the thermoelastic response of fiber-reinforced composite plates, as opposed to metal plates¹⁰, is apparently a consequence of the high-modulus, low-density characteristics of the composites.

Fig. 6 Histories of w_1 and w at the center of a $0^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ$ plate, clamped at $y = \pm 5$ in.

Fig. 7 Histories of w_1 and w at (a) $x=5$ in, $y=0$ and (b) $x=1.5$ in, $y=0$ of a $90^\circ/0^\circ/90^\circ$ plate, clamped at $y = \pm 5$ in.

The present results also indicate that the cross-ply stacking sequence can have a significant influence upon both the deformed shape and the deflection amplitudes of thermally loaded laminated plates. Additional results which have been obtained, including effects of the number of layers and aspect ratio upon the response, are omitted here due to space limitations but will be reported subsequently.

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